

1 FRONT MATTER

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3 **Title**

- 4 • Large-FOV 3D localization microscopy by spatially variant point spread function
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- 5 generation.

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22 **Abstract**23 Accurate characterization of the microscopic point spread function (PSF) is crucial for
24 achieving high-performance localization microscopy (LM). Traditionally, LM assumes a
25 spatially-invariant PSF to simplify the modeling of the imaging system. However, for large
26 fields of view (FOV) imaging, it becomes important to account for the spatially variant
27 nature of the PSF. In this work, we propose an accurate and fast principal component
28 analysis (PCA)-based field-dependent 3D PSF generator (PPG3D) and localizer for LM.
29 Through simulations and experimental 3D single molecule localization microscopy
30 (SMLM), we demonstrate the effectiveness of PPG3D, enabling super-resolution imaging
31 of mitochondria and microtubules with high fidelity over a large FOV. A comparison of
32 PPG3D with a shift-variant PSF generator for 3D LM reveals a three-fold improvement in
33 accuracy. Moreover, PPG3D is approximately one hundred times faster than existing PSF
34 generators, when used in image-plane-based interpolation mode. Given its user-friendliness,
35 we believe that PPG3D holds great potential for widespread application in SMLM and other
36 imaging modalities.37
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39 **Teaser**40 Spatially varying point spread function characterization enables 3D localization microscopy
41 over a large field of view.
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Introduction

Localization microscopy (LM) is a powerful imaging modality both for super-resolution imaging(1, 2) and for particle tracking(3). Imaging in these modalities is based on determining the positions of point sources or emitters with sub-diffraction precision.

Emitters from a flat sample can be localized to yield a 2D image. However, in the case of a volumetric sample, 3D LM is needed. One approach for 3D LM is PSF engineering, which intentionally induces aberrations at the pupil plane of an imaging system to yield an informative depth-dependent PSF, e.g., astigmatism(4), double-helix(5, 6), or tetrapod(7). For the decoding part, common localization algorithms include maximum likelihood estimation(8–12) and more recently, deep-learning-based algorithms, e.g., DeepSTORM3D(13), DECODE(14) and more(9, 15–18), which have demonstrated excellent performance when dealing with PSF overlap and high emitter-density. Considering the influence of field position on localization (field-dependent localization), recent work(19) proposes FD-DeepLoc by combining DECODE with CoorConv(20) to both address the field dependence and estimate emitter positions. Importantly, all estimators rely on some forward model, a PSF generator, i.e., a continuous-domain “dictionary” that maps an emitter’s 3D spatial position to a PSF. The performance of LM strongly depends on the accuracy of this PSF generator(21).

In its basic form, a PSF generator receives as input the optical system parameters and a 3D position and outputs the expected image on the camera of an emitter in that position. The generator is considered shift-invariant if the shape of its image is independent of the global transverse position of the emitter, which simplifies the PSF’s spatial dependence to be depth-only.

Shift-invariant PSF characterization is typically based on a physical model(22, 23), with additional experimental input to account for unavoidable aberrations and deviations from the ideal models. A commonly used analytical model for the 3D microscopic PSF is based on the principle that the PSF can be obtained by taking the absolute value squared of the Fourier transform of the field at the Back Focal Plane (BFP)(24); emitter defocus manifests as an approximately quadratic phase added to the BFP field. The experimental input can be acquired through a calibration experiment, where the PSF is measured at various known axial positions. Then, combining the calibration with the analytical model involves solving a phase-retrieval problem(12, 25) to determine the BFP phase profile that aligns with the experimental calibration measurement. This BFP phase profile can be projected onto Zernike polynomials, for computational efficiency, to yield Zernike pupil phase retrieval (ZPPR)(26, 27). For improved performance, a pixel-wise pupil representation can be used, at a cost of more optimization parameters, yielding VIPR (short for vectorial implementation of phase retrieval)(24). In addition to these model-based approaches, model-free generators utilize polynomial B-spline(28), C-spline(29, 30) basis, and Zernike moments/basis(31) to represent the depth-dependent PSF and yield PSF interpolation.

A common and important problem in LM is addressing field dependence of large FOV, because the shift-invariant assumption, deviates from reality in several cases. First, objectives, especially high-numerical-aperture ones widely used in SMLM, exhibit inherent field-dependent aberrations that vary with transverse positions(27, 32). Second, PSF engineering in 3D LM introduces additional optical elements that inevitably add some field dependence, e.g., due to some displacement of the phase element from the BFP. Third, field

dependence becomes more prominent as FOV increases(19, 33, 34), which is increasingly relevant in high-throughput imaging scenarios. Therefore, for 3D LM at high fidelity over a large FOV, the development of a PSF generator that considers both depth and field dependence would be highly beneficial.

In the context of LM, to the best of our knowledge, the only PSF generator that consider field dependence are based on ZPPR. Shift-variant ZPPR algorithms(19, 27, 35) rely on calibration measurements at many field positions to retrieve a Zernike-polynomial-based pupil phase for each position. Then, interpolation (32, 36, 37) of the Zernike basis coefficients is implemented to obtain the pupil phase corresponding to any desired field positions. In other fields, e.g., astronomy(38) and computational volumetric imaging(39, 40), field dependence has been characterized through truncated singular value decomposition (TSVD) of calibrated PSFs and interpolation of the decomposition coefficients.

Here, we extend the PSF decomposition and interpolation concept and propose a fast and accurate spatially variant PSF generator in 3D (PPG3D) specifically designed for SMLM. PPG3D is a continuous-domain PSF model which implements principal component analysis (PCA) of calibrated PSFs, conducts local interpolation of those principal component (PC) coefficients, and then generates the PSF at any target position through backward space projection. Comparison of PPG3D with three other commonly-used PSF generators in LM demonstrates improvements of over three times in accuracy and around a hundred times in computation speed. In its application to SMLM, we combine PPG3D with our localization estimator FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D, customized from one of the state-of-art localization estimators, DeepSTORM3D(13), and achieve 3D super-resolution imaging of mitochondria and microtubules with high fidelity over a large FOV.

Results

1. PPG3D

PPG3D formation

PPG3D is a PSF interpolator built upon calibrated PSFs at known spatial positions. Direct pixel-by-pixel interpolation of the measured PSF is prone to failure due to sensitivity to noise and ill-posedness. To address this issue, we employ PCA of the measured PSFs (Fig. 1A) and perform 3D interpolation in a lower dimensional space (Fig. 1B). Because lateral-position-dependence is more moderate compared to depth dependence for PSF of SMLM, we separate the 3D interpolation into two 2D lateral interpolations and one 1D axial interpolation. Furthermore, we empirically find that a PSF in LM can be adequately represented by its surrounding PSFs. As a result, we employ local linear interpolation among six PSFs, specifically measured at three lateral positions and two axial positions (Fig. 1B), to improve the operation speed.

Fig. 1. Schematic of PSF engineering and PPG3D. (A) PSF engineering with a Tetrapod phase mask at the back focal plane (BFP) and experimentally measured PSFs at two field positions xy_1 and xy_2 (white squares in Fig. 2 A) exemplifying field dependence. IIP denotes intermediate imaging plane. (B) PSF at any desired position (green star) is interpolated using six measured PSFs at nearby calibrated positions (red dots). Each lateral position corresponds to a z-stack of a depth-dependent Tetrapod PSF. The bottom flowchart shows two separate steps in PPG3D: lateral (gray arrows) and axial interpolations (blue arrow).

To generate a PSF at any spatial position, we first search for three lateral calibration positions close to the target coordinate according to a criterion of even distribution (# 3 of Supplementary Text (ST)), at two axial planes above and below the target axial position, such that a total of six PSFs are chosen. Next, PCA of selected PSFs at each axial plane is conducted and lateral 2D interpolations regarding PC coefficients are performed to address field dependence, which yields two PSFs, located at the blue dots in Fig. 1B. The following step is PCA of those two laterally interpolated PSFs and a 1D interpolation of the PC coefficients, followed by a transformation back to image space, to yield the final target PSF. More details of this implementation in #3 of ST and field dependence quantification is presented in #5 of ST.

Comparison of PPG3D with PSF generators in LM

The comparison is performed upon an experimental calibration dataset (151 lateral positions by 29 axial positions) obtained from an imaging system with tetrapod PSF engineering (see imaging system #1 of Table S1). Each cropped PSF has a cropped size of 81×81 pixels (#2 of ST). We divide the comparison into the shift-invariant case, i.e., axial-only interpolation, and the shift-variant case, i.e., axial and lateral interpolation. The criteria for assessing different generators include Pearson's correlation coefficient (CC) defined as Eq. S1, root mean square error (RMSE), comparing measured PSFs to generated ones, as well as runtime.

We first compare PPG3D's shift-invariant mode with three shift-invariant PSF generators: model-based VIPR and ZPPR21 (which uses 21 Zernike basis functions for pupil function representation), and a model-free Spline interpolator. At the field position P_0 in Fig. 2A, near the center of the FOV, PSFs are measured at a series of axial positions (Fig. 2B horizontal axis) which are divided into a "seen" group and an "unseen" group (marked by

grid lines in Fig. 2B. The former is set as input for PSF generation and the latter is used for test. The details of implementing VIPR, ZPPR21, and Spline are shown in #3 of ST. Firstly, PPG3D exhibits larger CC and lower RMSE, compared with others, at “unseen” axial positions, which is also visually demonstrated by generated PSFs at a test position (black dot line in Fig. 2B) in Fig. 2C. Secondly, PSFs generated at “seen” positions by PPG3D are nearly identical to the measured ones, while all other generators exhibit some characterization errors. Thirdly, among the two model-based generators, VIPR outperforms ZPPR21, thanks to its pixel-wise optimization. Finally, in terms of runtime (from data input to generating all the unseen test data) measured through the code we can access (Table S5), PPG3D is around 100 times faster than the second fastest algorithm, which is ZPPR21 (Fig. 2D).

Fig. 2. Comparison of PPG3D with three PSF generators in LM. (A) A FOV with 151 calibrated field positions (gray and red dots), among which xy_1 and xy_2 are used for demonstration in Fig. 1. Scale bar: 20 μm . The comparison is divided into shift-invariant mode B-E considering point P_0 in A, and shift-variant mode F-H where the red dots are set as unseen test positions. (B) CC and RMSE assessment of, VIPR, Spline, PPG3D, and ZPPR21 (implementation details in Fig. S3). The axial positions at grid lines are set as unseen test positions. (C) Generated PSFs at the black dash line of B. (D) RMSE-time comprehensive assessment (details in Table S5). (E) Principal components used in PPG3D and their variance ratios. (F) CC and RMSE assessment of shift-variant ZPPR21 and PPG3D at the five test positions. (G) Generated PSFs at the lateral test positions and one

axial position (black dash line in F). **(H)** RMSE-time comprehensive assessment. Scale bar at C, E and G: 2 μm .

Next, we compare PPG3D's shift-variant mode with shift variant ZPPR21. Among all the calibrated field positions, we choose 5 as unseen test positions (red dots in Fig. 2A). At all 5-by-29 test spatial positions, PPG3D performs better in both CC and RMSE than ZPPR21 (Fig. 2F). The implementation details of shift-variant ZPPR21 are presented in ST #3 and Fig. S3. Specifically, ZPPR21 fails to characterize the central bright spot of measured PSFs (Fig. 2G), caused by unmodulated light at the BFP, which often occurs due to some mismatch between the phase-mask size and the actual light circle at the BFP. Meanwhile, PPG3D is hundreds of times faster than shift-variant ZPPR21, which is important for applications such as online training of deep-learning-based localization algorithms. **Note that the comparison here is based on bead images on the coverslip and there is no refractive-index-mismatch issue.** We also analyzed PPG3D's generalizability for other PSFs (Fig. S4-S6 which also show the performance at FOV edge), calibration density, and robustness to noise (Fig. S7).

2. High-accuracy large-FOV 3D SMLM

A field-dependent localization estimator: FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D

We construct a complete field-dependent 3D SMLM localizer, by combining PPG3D with DeepSTORM3D(13), a deep learning-based algorithm for 3D SMLM localization, generating a large-FOV field-dependent localization estimator: FOV-dependent-DeepSTORM3D. This is based on the addition of a CoordConv(20) to all the feature detection layers of DeepSTORM3D (Fig. 3A) which consists of 6 convolution layers (constant feature channel number of 64) with skip connections in between (41) To overcome the computational challenges from the large FOV reconstruction, we employ a segmentation and consolidation scheme which involves cropping the complete image into sub-images for localization and subsequently stitching together the localization results. Notably, PPG3D can be combined with localizers other than DeepSTORM3D, e.g. DECODE(14), which is used in FD-DeepLoc(19).

In the training phase, training images consist of generated sub-images with random PSFs placed away from the sub-image edges to prevent PSF truncation. During the inference phase, we divide each experimental image into sub-images with some overlap. These sub-images are then fed individually into the network to obtain localizations, and the localizations from all sub-images are fused to generate the complete global localization map for the frame. To ensure accuracy, unreliable localizations near the edges of each sub-image are excluded, focusing only on the central valid area. Notably, this exclusion does not result in localization loss due to our precise cropping overlap design (Fig. S10A).

Fig. 3. FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D and one prediction demonstration. (A) FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D outline. Based on DeepSTORM3D, x and y maps corresponding to the cropped sub-image are fed to feature extraction layers and prediction layers to yield local localizations, which are then filtered and transformed into final global localizations. (B) Demonstration of one representative experimental frame (upper left triangle) and a rendered image (bottom right triangle) which is an overlay, upon this frame, consisting of the reconstructed PSFs according to the network inference. The zoom-in view (1) exemplifies this overlay in a square with the experimental measurement (2) and PSF reconstruction (3). Scale bar = 10 μm .

Network training and inference on simulated data

Using PPG3D, we generate field dependent training data for FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D, which divides the whole FOV into 121 patches (each has 161 pixels in both width and height) in a 11-by-11 grid with some overlap (Fig. S10A). The bottom-left 6-by-6 patches, around a quarter of the whole calibrated FOV, are used to demonstrate our concept in simulation. For comparison, we also train a standard DeepSTORM3D with the same training images which, however, are from the shift-invariant mode of PPG3D. First, we simulate 240 random emitters and test localization accuracy according to RMSE. Note that both networks, in the prediction stage, use a threshold regarding prediction confidence. Because the same threshold for both networks yields a different number of localizations in the same image, we set a series of thresholds and show a plot of localization RMSE vs. the number of predictions. Furthermore, for each threshold, we repeat the inference ten times with different random emitters. The lateral and axial RMSE between the predicted localizations and ground truth are calculated for assessment (Fig. 4A-B). On average, FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D improves the lateral and axial localization accuracy by 36% and 30% respectively. The accuracy and precision as a function of position in the FOV are analyzed in Fig. S11.

Fig. 4. Comparison of FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (subscript 1) to DeepSTORM3D (subscript 2) in simulation. (A) Lateral RMSE of predictions with respect to the number of emitters detected by both networks. (B) Same comparison regarding axial RMSE. (C) Maximum projection of the reconstructed 3D dotted tubular “C” structure by FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D. Scale bar: 10 μm . The cross sections along the lines D, F, G, and H are in (D), (F), (G), and (H), and a zoom-in view of E at $z = 6.175 \mu\text{m}$ is shown in (E). Scale bar: 0.5 μm . The intensity profile along I in F, J in G, and K in H are shown in (I), (J), (K) with the same color correspondence. The blue line on the top of I shows the true diameter of the simulated tube--300 nm.

Secondly, we create a 3D structure with 3x3 pattern of “CCCC”. Each unit is composed of 16 dotted tubules, each of which has a diameter of 300 nm, length of 3 μm , and consists of 3200 emitters (Fig. S12). Simulating the emitter blinking in a SMLM experiment, we predict the structure using 4000 frames of simulated images. When processing those images through both networks, we ensure the same approximate number of interferences through filters in ThunderSTORM (42) (ST #7). As the reconstruction (Fig. 4C-K, Movie S7) shows, FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (subscript 1 in Fig. 4) outperforms standard DeepSTORM3D (subscript 2) and yields super-resolution reconstruction with higher fidelity. Specifically, Fig. 4D₂ shows noisier and deformed reconstructed tubules, which is improved and corrected in Fig. 4D₁. Similarly, Fig. 4E₁ presents a clearer hollow tubule structure compared with Fig. 4E₂. More detailed quantification comparisons regarding

266 hollow structure (Fig. 4D-H) and intensity profiles (Fig. 4I-K) demonstrate that FOV-
267 dependent DeepSTORM3D helps correct misestimations caused by field dependence. An
268 additional simulation of a sinusoidal surface is shown in Fig. S13.

269 Experimental demonstration: super-resolution imaging of mitochondria and microtubules

270 We perform 3D STORM using the Tetrapod PSF (imaging system #2 in Table S1). The
271 experiment consists of imaging a fluorescently labeled samples as the fluorophores blink in
272 time (Movie S1), localizing them, and reconstructing a super-resolved image using either
273 FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D or DeepSTORM3D. See experimental details in the
274 Methods section. We first image mitochondria, over a calibration FOV of 178-by-178 μm ;
275 in total, 52261 frames (see one example frame with rendering prediction in Fig. 3B and
276 Movie S1) were processed; and ~ 12.7 million valid localizations were found (see the
277 reconstruction demonstration in Movie S2-4). Comparing the localization results (Fig. 5)
278 from FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (subscript 1) and DeepSTORM3D (subscript 2), the
279 improvement is noticeable. In Fig. 5, our results outperform their counterparts, with regards
280 to localization density (color brightness) of the reconstructed microstructures and the noise
281 (spotty patterns) around. Specifically, Fig. 5D₁ shows a sharper pink and orange structure
282 compared with Fig. 5D₂. Also, Fig. 5E₁ and F₁ show less speckled and noise structures in
283 comparison to Fig. 5E₂ and F₂. Furthermore, in the cross sections G-J, as well as the more
284 quantitative intensity profiles in K-N, our method yields brighter, less noisy, and more
285 recognizable cavity structures. We also imaged microtubules (Fig. S14) in this setup.

286

287
 288 **Fig. 5. Large-FOV 3D super-resolution imaging of mitochondria with Tetrapod PSF.**
 289 (A) Super-resolved 3D mitochondria image (maximum projection) in a 127-by-160 μm^2
 290 FOV through FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (subscript 1). The zoom-in views of square
 291 regions B and C are shown in (B) and (C). The comparison, with the reconstruction from
 292 DeepSTORM3D (subscript 2), regarding regions D and E in B, and F in C are shown in (D),
 293 (E), and (F) respectively. The white arrows indicate some noteworthy details. The cross
 294 sections along lines G and I in B, and J and H in C, are shown in (G), (I), (J), and (H). The
 295 intensity profiles along lines in those cross sections are shown in (K-N). The blue and
 296 orange lines correspond to FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D and DeepSTORM3D,
 297 respectively. Scale bars in A-C: 20 μm . The rest scale bars: 2 μm .

298 Next, we used a cylindrical lens with a focal length of 500 mm to generate an astigmatic
 299 PSF (Fig. S10B) for 3D SMLM. We calibrated 424 field positions (Fig. S10B) and fed this
 300 PSF data to PPG3D to build the spatially dependent PSF model for FOV-dependent
 301 DeepSTORM3D. Again, we used both mitochondria and microtubules, and the
 302 reconstruction results (Movie S5-6), as well as the comparison with regular
 303 DeepSTORM3D (subscript 2), are shown in Fig. 6. Compared with cross sections (Fig. 6B-
 304 D, G-H) with subscript 2, the reconstructed structures from our method (subscript 1) appear
 305 more complete, in the sense that the density of the localization is higher. For example, the
 306 reconstruction is less ‘patchy’, around the mitochondrial cavity and along the microtubule
 307 line in the FOV-dependent case compared to the FOV-independent case.

308
 309 **Fig. 6. Large-FOV 3D super-resolution imaging of mitochondria (A-D) and**
 310 **microtubules (E-H) with an astigmatic PSF. (A) Maximum projection of the**
 311 **reconstructed mitochondria with xy cross section (B) at $z=0.36 \mu\text{m}$ in the box B, xz cross**
 312 **section (C) and (D) along the line C and D respectively. Subscript 1 and 2 represent FOV-**
 313 **Dependent DeepSTORM3D and DeepSTORM3D. (E) Maximum projection of the**
 314 **reconstructed microtubules with a zoom-in view (F) showing the region between two nuclei,**
 315 **and xy cross sections (G) and (H) in boxes G, H, and I in E. Scale bars in A and E: $20 \mu\text{m}$.**
 316 **Scale bars in B, D, G and H: $2 \mu\text{m}$. Scale bar in C: $1 \mu\text{m}$. Scale bar in F: $10 \mu\text{m}$.**

Discussion

In this work we demonstrate a field-dependent dense localization method for 3D SMLM. The method consists of two main components. First, we introduce PPG3D, a spatially variant PSF generator that employs PCA-based interpolation. This approach involves transforming PSFs into a lower-dimensional space, conducting interpolation for a target spatial position, and projecting back to the image space to obtain the desired PSF. Comparative analysis with other PSF generators in LM showcases substantial enhancement in accuracy and operation speed. Next, we integrate PPG3D with DeepSTORM3D to address field dependence in large-FOV 3D LM, resulting in FOV-dependent-DeepSTORM3D. This new localization estimator demonstrates an improvement in prediction accuracy by over 30%. In STORM experiments, FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D enables 3D super-resolution imaging of mitochondria and microtubules within a large FOV, exhibiting noticeably higher fidelity compared to standard DeepSTORM3D.

PPG3D offers a fundamental advantage in its simplicity, stemming from its interpolation nature, compared to model-based PSF generators. Reliable implementation of model-based generators often requires users to accurately retrieve physical parameters and comprehend physical models. In contrast, the PPG3D codes we provide only require calibrated PSFs and positions as input to accurately perform PSF generation, making it potentially more user-friendly. Furthermore, the dimensionality reduction achieved through PCA confers a substantial speed advantage to PPG3D, as it involves interpolating a smaller number of parameters. When compared to the shift variant ZPPR21, PPG3D not only demonstrates superior accuracy and speed but also requires fewer calibration positions.

While PSF generators based on decomposition and interpolation can be found in other fields, such as astronomy and computational volumetric imaging, PPG3D distinguishes itself from them in two key aspects. Firstly, PPG3D stands out as a genuine 3D continuous-domain PSF generator. In contrast, shift-variant PSF generation in astronomy(38) is primarily conducted in 2D. Although volumetric imaging(39, 40) requires a 3D PSF, the voxel representation of objects dictates that the PSF is pixelated by 3D voxel. Secondly, PPG3D employs a concise and efficient scheme of local interpolations, allowing for high-speed operation without any concerns regarding memory limitations. In comparison, other studies(39, 40) often resort to decomposing all the calibrated PSFs, which can pose challenges regarding memory efficiency.

However, the absence of a physical model limits PPG3D when the influence of refractive index mismatch is prominent. This limitation can be addressed, by combining a shift-invariant model-based PSF generator with PPG3D. For FOV-dependent-DeepSTORM3D, it enables field dependence learning, however cropping the whole FOV into many fixed sub-areas in advance is still naïve and lacks flexibility. A possible future direction can be to improve the flexibility of our method e.g., by randomly sampling the sub-images in the training stage and ultimately alleviating the need for positional encoding.

Finally, the combination of a field-dependent PSF generator with a deep learning-based localizer, presented here, can be used in a variety of scenarios, including where the PSF is controllably different throughout the FOV(43).

Materials and Methods

1. Formulation of spatially variant PSF

364 The PSF is the impulse response of a system, which, in the imaging context, is the 3D
365 electromagnetic field distribution at the image domain, in response to a point source at the
366 object domain. For shift-invariant imaging systems, the PSF can be described, up to scaling
367 and inversion, by:

$$H\{\delta(x - \alpha, y - \beta, z - \gamma)\} = h(x' - \alpha, y' - \beta, z' - \gamma) \quad (1)$$

368 where H is the 3D transfer function, δ is the delta function, (x, y, z) are spatial coordinates
369 of object side and (x', y', z') are for the image side, (α, β, γ) is the spatial position of the
370 point source, and h is the 3D shape of the PSF. Note that we ignore the magnification effect
371 for simplicity. If we abandon the shift-invariant assumption and consider the more general
372 case, the PSF formation process can be given by:

$$H\{\delta(x - \alpha, y - \beta, z - \gamma)\} = h_{\alpha\beta\gamma}(x', y', z') \quad (2)$$

373 where now PSF $h_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is dependent on the location of the point source and the PSF shape
374 changes as we move the point source in 3D object space. In practice, cameras with 2D
375 sensors are typically used in imaging systems to sample the 3D space in a 2D plane.
376 Switching to a 2D case, the impulse response becomes:

$$H\{\delta(x - \alpha, y - \beta, z - \gamma)\} = h_{\alpha\beta\gamma}(x', y') \quad (3)$$

377 The PSF most obviously changes with the axial coordinate γ , related to the concepts of
378 “focus”, “defocus”, and “depth of field (DOF)”. In comparison, $\alpha\beta$ dependence is much
379 milder and is typically ignored, for the sake of simple calculations. Generally, the former is
380 called depth dependence and the latter is called field dependence, and the systems exhibiting
381 field dependence are shift-variant. Our goal is to build a PSF generator that considers both
382 kinds of dependence, for LM.

383 The basic idea of PPG3D is to transform the calibrated PSFs to a space with reduced
384 dimensionality through PCA, specifically truncated singular value decomposition, and then
385 implement interpolation in this low-dimensional domain with respect to the spatial position
386 (α, β, γ) . It is worth mentioning that, under this concept, different PCA interpolation
387 schemes can be designed, dependent on the specific goal.

388 2. Imaging system calibration

389 To conduct the calibration experiment in a large FOV, two factors should be considered:
390 point source distribution throughout the FOV, and homogeneous illumination. In this work,
391 we use both fluorescent bead samples and a nano-hole array (Table S2) and rely on axial
392 sample scanning by a microscope stage. For illumination, we built an illumination system
393 composed of a 2-W high-power laser, a multi-mode fiber, and a vibration motor. Notably,
394 SMLM experiment often benefits from strong illumination to enable efficient biomolecule
395 blinking.

396 In the imaging system used for the STORM experiment, PSF engineering is performed using
397 a Tetrapod diffractive optical element (7). We use a fluorescent bead sample immersed in
398 water for calibration. After many times of lateral scanning, 334 field positions are covered
399 within a circular FOV with a diameter of $\sim 180 \mu\text{m}$. At each field position, the PSF is
400 measured in an axial range of $(-3, 3) \mu\text{m}$ at an interval of $0.15 \mu\text{m}$. Thus, in total, this
401 calibration consists of 334-by-41 spatial positions.

402 **As we mentioned in Discussion, we include the possibility of using physical models to**
403 **address** refractive index (RI) mismatch issue, i.e., the RI difference between the sample
404 medium and the objective immersion oil. The image of a fluorescent source (e.g., sub-
405 diffraction bead) on a glass coverslip is different from that of a fluorescent source inside a

406 sample (Fig. S9); this is why the PSF derived by straight-forward interpolation of a z-stack
407 of a bead on a glass coverslip cannot be used directly to obtain the PSF of a defocused
408 emitter inside practically any biological medium at high accuracy.

409 Theoretically, the existence of the RI mismatch (13, 24) introduces two axial parameters
410 with different contributions (#6 of ST) to the phase at BFP: the distance of an emitter from
411 the coverslip, and the position of the nominal focal plane (NFP), i.e. the focal plane without
412 RI mismatch. In calibration, we can only change the NFP positions, while the real
413 experiment has fixed NFP and unknown various emitter positions. To transform the
414 calibration measurements to be applicable to the RI mismatch case, we use model-based
415 VIPR(24). Specifically, we rely on the imaging model from VIPR to search for a proper
416 NFP position such that the lowest emitter in experiment can be covered by the model. Then
417 we fix the NFP and generate PSFs for the emitter at a series of distances relative to the
418 coverslip. By doing so, we obtain a new PSF dataset with 334 field positions in a 180 μm -
419 diameter FOV and 28 axial positions over a 4 μm range. PPG3D based on this dataset can
420 now be used to generate shift-variant PSFs of emitters.

421 3. Sample preparation for STORM experiment

422 22×22 mm, 170 μm cover glasses (Deckgläser, No.1.5H) were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath
423 with 5% Contrad 70 (Decon) at 60°C for 30 min, then washed twice with double distilled
424 water (incubated shaking for 10 min each time), incubated shaking in ethanol absolute for
425 30 min, sterilized with filtered 70% ethanol for 30 min and dried in a biological cabinet.
426 COS7 cells at a concentration of 60,000 cells/ml in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
427 (DMEM) with 1g/l D-glucose (Sartorius, 01-050-1A), supplemented with fetal bovine
428 serum (Biological Industries, 04-007-1A), penicillin-streptomycin (Biological Industries,
429 03-031-1B) and glutamine (Biological Industries, 03- 020-1B), were grown for 24 hr in a
430 6-well plate (Thermo Fisher, Nunclon Delta Surface) containing 6 ml of the cell suspension
431 and the cleaned cover glasses, at 37°C, and 5% CO₂. The cells were fixed with 4%
432 paraformaldehyde and 0.2% glutaraldehyde in PBS, pH 6.2, for 60 min, washed and
433 incubated in 0.3M glycine/PBS solution for 10 minutes. The cover glasses were transferred
434 into a clean 6-well plate and incubated in a blocking solution for 2 hr (10% goat serum, 3%
435 BSA, 2.2% glycine, and 0.1% Triton-X in PBS, filtered with 0.45 μm Millex PVDF filter
436 unit). The cells were then immune-stained with either 1:500 diluted anti-TOMM20-AF647
437 antibody (Abcam, ab209606) or 1:500 diluted anti-alpha-tubulin-AF647 (ab190573) and
438 1:500 diluted anti-beta-tubulin-AF647 (Abcam, ab235759) in the blocking buffer for 1.5 hr
439 and washed five times with PBS. For super-resolution imaging, a PDMS chamber (22x22x3
440 mm, with a 13x13 mm hole cut in the middle) was attached to the cover glass containing
441 the fixed and stained COS7 cells to create a pool for the blinking buffer. Blinking buffer (50
442 mM Cysteamine hydrochloride (Sigma, M6500), 20% sodium lactate solution (Sigma,
443 L1375), and 3% OxyFluor (Sigma, SAE0059) in PBS, pH 8-8.5) was added and a cover
444 glass was placed on top while ensuring minimal air bubbles.

445 4. STORM Imaging

446 We used the Nikon eclipse Ti2 inverted microscope equipped with N-STORM unit (Nikon),
447 silicone-oil objective (Nikon, RS HP Plan Apo 100x/1.35 Sil WD), and a multi-bandpass
448 dichroic (Semrock, Di03-R405-488-532-635-t3). The microscope was extended with a 4f
449 system (f=200 mm) containing a tetrapod phase mask in the Fourier plane and a sCMOS
450 camera (Teledyne Photometrics, Kinetix) for image acquisition. In the astigmatism case, we
451 put, in a 4f system (f=200 mm), a cylindrical lens with a 500 mm focal length in front of
452 another camera (Teledyne Photometrics Prime 95B). The sample was illuminated by a 640
453 nm, laser at estimated power of ~3.13 kW/cm² at the sample.

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567

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590

591 **Competing interests:** The authors declare they have no competing interests.

592

593 **Data and materials availability:**

594 All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and/or the
595 Supplementary Materials.

596 PPG3D: <https://github.com/dafeixiao/PPG3D>

597 FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D: [https://github.com/dafeixiao/FOV-dependent-
598 DeepSTORM3D](https://github.com/dafeixiao/FOV-dependent-DeepSTORM3D)

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607 **Supplementary Materials**

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ScienceAdvances

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Supplementary Materials for

Large-FOV 3D localization microscopy by spatially variant point spread function generation

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This PDF file includes:

Supplementary Text
Figs. S1 to S14
Tables S1 to S5
Movies S1 to S7

Supplementary Text

1. Optical imaging systems

The imaging systems involved in this work can be illustrated as Fig. S1 and their detailed compositions and parameters are presented in Table S1. The samples we used for calibration and super-resolution imaging tasks are described in Table S2. For PPG3D's demonstration and comparisons (Fig. 2) with other point spread function (PSF) generators in LM, the image system # 1 with an oil objective (1.35 NA, 100 magnification) and bead samples are used. For the field dependence quantification (Fig. S8), we used the image system # 1 with an air objective (0.75 NA, 40 magnification) and the nanohole array. The STORM experiments were implemented in imaging system # 2 with the oil objective (1.35 NA, 100 magnification) and bead samples were used for calibration.

2. Processing image stacks from calibration experiments

The shift-invariant mode or axial mode of PPG3D simply receives a PSF stack with the corresponding axial positions. For shift-variant mode, we need to input a package of 4-dimensional PSF dataset, a list of lateral positions and another list of axial positions. The dimensions of the PSF dataset are the number of lateral positions, axial positions, and pixels in height and width. To crop PSFs from the calibrated images, PSF center detection is required and we resort to cross-correlation and template matching to achieve that. With an example of processing one image stack, we follow four steps.

- 1) choose one image (superposition of many PSFs at one axial plane) from the stack and manually crop one PSF as the template.
- 2) calculate the cross correlation of the cropped PSF template with the chosen image.
- 3) search for peaks of the correlation result. Peak detection without the prior knowledge of the peak number is not a seemingly easy task. Here we first resort to a coarse but fast algorithm [33] which can reach the approximate region around the real peaks, and then apply Gaussian fitting near the approximately searched peaks to find a fine detection with a sub-pixel accuracy.
- 4) crop the image stack according to the searched PSF centers and form the 4D PSF dataset.

660 After processing all the image stacks, we filter out field positions very close to each other.
661 Finally, we combine the valid field positions and axial positions and obtain the input of PPG3D.

662 **3. Implementation details of PPG3D, VIPR, ZPPR21, and Spline**

663 As mentioned in the main text, for one PSF interpolation in 3D, we use three calibrated field
664 positions, two axial positions, and total six spatial calibration positions. The searching criterion
665 regarding those positions consists of following procedures:

- 666 1) calculate lateral distances of the target position from all the calibrated positions.
- 667 2) choose a certain number of closest positions from which we combine any three of them to
668 form a triangle.
- 669 3) calculate the centroid of each triangle.
- 670 4) choose the centroid closest to the target position and the corresponding three field positions
671 are the final selection (see Fig. S2A).
- 672 5) the two axial planes are chosen simply in terms of axial distance.

673 One example about the field position selection and interpolation is shown in Fig. S2. For PCA,
674 we use Python class `sklearn.decomposition.PCA` and set 0.95 as the total percentage of variance
675 which needs to be explained, which yields 15 principal components in the case of Fig. 2.

676 VIPR [18] aims at retrieving a pixel-wise phase mask at BFP to characterize the deviations of
677 a practical imaging system from the ideal imaging model (scalar or vectorial). ZPPR21, short for
678 Zernike-polynomial pupil phase retrieval, differs from the VIPR concept in the pupil formulation.
679 For the imaging system # 1 in table S1, the retrieved phases from both methods are shown in Fig.
680 S3A-B. When it comes to shift-variant ZPPR21, the regular ZPPR21 is implemented to yield one
681 vector of Zernike coefficients at each calibrated field position from which vectors at any other non-
682 calibrated positions are interpolated. Based on data in the Fig. 2 of the main text, one example of
683 such interpolation is shown in Fig. S3C. Specifically, 146-by-21 Zernike coefficients are retrieved
684 at 146 field positions and another 5 “unseen” positions (marked as red cross dot in Fig. S3C) are
685 for test. One might argue that 21-degree Zernike polynomial cannot well characterize Tetrapod
686 PSF. Unluckily, due to the ZPPR21 code limitation, we cannot apply a higher degree. To further
687 qualify the comparison between ZPPR21 and PPG3D, we switch to Astigmatism PSF (Fig. S3F-H)
688 and again saw better performance in PPG3D.

690 **4. Analysis of PPG3D: generalizability, calibration density, and noise robustness**

691 For this analysis, we did another experiment in imaging setup #1 of Table S1 with one exception,
692 which is that we used the Teledyne Photometrics **Kinetix** camera here. On the spatial light
693 modulator, we placed phase masks (Fig. S1 (C-E)) for PSF engineering. For each PSF type, we
694 obtained a calibration dataset which is composed of three parts: one 1D axial position list, one 2D
695 lateral position array, and 4D PSF data (the same #2 of ST). The details of the three datasets
696 regarding the double helix, astigmatism and the learned PSF are given in Table S4.

697 We analyzed these data from three aspects: PSF characterization accuracy, density of the
698 calibration points, as well as robustness to noise.

700 1) PSF characterization accuracy

701 As we did in the main text, we examined PPG3D’s PSF characterization accuracy from axial
702 (z/axial dependence) and global (xyz/spatial dependence) perspectives. Firstly, for axial
703 interpolation, we focused on one field position with one PSF z-stack corresponding to a z position
704 list which is split into a “seen” half for interpolation and an “unseen” half for test. For the
705 assessment metric, we used Pearson’s correlation coefficient (CC) defined as Eq. S1 where PSF_g
706 and PSF_m are generated PSF and measured PSF (using a bead sample) respectively; i denotes row
707 index; j denotes column index; the bar on top means average value.

$$r = \frac{\sum(PSF_g(i,j) - \overline{PSF_g})(PSF_m(i,j) - \overline{PSF_m})}{\sqrt{\sum(PSF_g(i,j) - \overline{PSF_g})^2 \sum(PSF_m(i,j) - \overline{PSF_m})^2}} \quad (S1)$$

This metric is used to evaluate the correlation of the generated PSF with the measured one. When doing principal component analysis (PCA) regarding the double helix PSFs at seen positions, we set the total explained variance as 0.99 and got 5 principal components (PCs) shown in Fig. S4B with the variance percentage of each PC above. After PCA-based PSF generation, we calculated the CCs at seen positions (Fig. S4A, dots which are not on the grid) and unseen positions (Fig. S4A, dots on the grid). The interpolated PSF at several unseen positions, together with the corresponding measured ones, are shown in Fig. S4C. This analysis demonstrates that PPG3D can faithfully characterize the depth dependence of double helix PSF.

For global interpolation, using the double helix PSF dataset, we have 437 calibrated field positions among which we chose 5 as unseen position for test (orange circles at the bottom projection of Fig. S4D. Hereafter, orange marks represent test positions) and used the rest (blue cross mark at the bottom projection of Fig. S4D) as the input of PPG3D. For each position, either seen or unseen, we applied PPG3D to generate a z-stack PSFs, and calculated the average CC (the blue or orange dot) with the measured PSF stack. To clearly show the CC distribution, we also projected the 3D CC dots to the left yz plane in Fig. S4D, which shows the overall CC above 0.9. For visual demonstration, we also showed the interpolated PSFs at the z=0 μm of the 5 unseen test positions in Fig. S4E which are well consistent with the measured ones.

Similarly, we analyzed the astigmatism dataset as well as the learned PSF dataset, as shown in Fig. S5 and Fig. S6 respectively. In general, PPG3D can accurately characterize PSF's depth dependence and field dependence of all PSF types we tested.

2) Density analysis

We chose the double helix PSF dataset and analyzed how the calibration density influences PPG3D's PSF characterization accuracy through three steps. First, we calculated a distance matrix of the lateral position array in the dataset through `scipy.spatial.distance_matrix`. Second, we defined a series of distance thresholds (`numpy.linspace(0.3, 20, 40)`, unit : μm) and, for each threshold, filtered out some neighboring calibration positions to reach a certain calibration density defined as the number of points per μm^2 . Finally, we applied to PPG3D under each density and assessed the accuracy in terms of CC (Fig. S7A). Compared with the dense case (Fig. S7C), a calibration that is too sparse (Fig. S7B) can cause PSF misrepresentations (see PSFs at P_2 and P_5 in Fig. S7D) due to insufficient local coverage. Higher density produces better accuracy, nevertheless, as a rough estimate, density of ~ 0.01 points per μm^2 already reaches close to the best performance.

3) Noise analysis

PPG3D aims at capturing PSF shape dependence on the axial and lateral position of a point source or emitter. Because the depth dependence is much stronger, compared with the field dependence, we focus this noise analysis on axial interpolation. Based on one field position of the double helix PSF dataset, we simulated two kinds of noise: shot noise and read-out noise.

When analyzing the influence of shot noise on PPG3D's PSF characterization accuracy, we followed three steps: normalizing the measured PSFs in terms of a series of emission photon numbers (`numpy.linspace(1000, 20000, 20)`), adding Poisson noise to the normalized PSF z-stack, and implementing PCA-based interpolation with accuracy assessment (Fig. S7E). As the photon number decreases (simulating a decrease in exposure time in an experiment), the shot noise becomes stronger and the interpolation becomes less accurate. However, even with a lowest number of photons tested (1000 in this case), the interpolated PSFs from PPG3D (Fig. S7G) still resemble the measured ones at a series of unseen test axial positions, showing good robustness.

755 Additionally, we used additive Gaussian noise to simulate read-out noise. We first implemented
756 photon normalization regarding the PSF z-stack and then added Gaussian noise with zero mean and
757 a series of standard deviations (`numpy.linspace(4, 200, 20)`, a simulation of different cameras in
758 experiment). The noisy PSF stack was then fed to PPG3D for PSF generation with accuracy
759 assessment (Fig. S7F) where the noise level H yields PSFs in Fig. S7H at a series of unseen test
760 positions. Although the data is very noisy, the interpolation can still faithfully reflect how the PSF
761 shape changes with axial positions.

762 **5. Field dependence quantification**

764 The utilization of PCA on calibrated PSFs can also serve to quantitatively characterize the field
765 dependence of an imaging system. Here, we use a nano-hole array for calibration in an imaging
766 system (optical setup #1 of Table S1) with a 40x objective. We captured PSFs at 234 field positions
767 (Fig. S8A) within an axial range of $(-3 \mu\text{m}, 3 \mu\text{m})$, with intervals of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$. To quantify the
768 difference of these PSFs relative to a central reference PSF at a specific axial plane, we employ
769 PCA-based Euclidean distance, which measures the vector distance in PCA space.

770 Initially, we computed the Euclidean distance and obtained non-circular field dependence, shown
771 as a contour plot (Fig. S8B). This plot reveals that the PSF changes more rapidly towards the right
772 side of the (FOV) (as indicated by the higher density of contour lines on the right). Additionally,
773 the measured PSF, at the right red spot below the contour plot, appears to be severely defocused,
774 which can be attributed to a slight tilt of the object slide or the microscope stage—a common
775 phenomenon encountered in large FOVs.

776 Notably, the tilt effect often exhibits a more pronounced field-dependent impact compared to
777 other sources of field dependence in an imaging system, such as aberrations introduced by the
778 objective lens or the PSF engineering module. To mitigate the influence of tilt, we employ a four-
779 step method for tilt detection:

- 780 1) Choose a reference field position.
- 781 2) Utilize PPG3D to axially interpolate PSFs at other field positions.
- 782 3) At each field position, identify the axial position where the PSF most closely resembles the
783 reference PSF.
- 784 4) Fit all searched axial positions to a tilted plane.

785 The detected tilt (Fig. S8C) demonstrates a maximum axial position difference of $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$. After
786 compensating for the tilt effect by subtracting the calculated tilt value at each calibrated position,
787 we reevaluated the field dependence (Fig. S8D), which now appears circularly distributed. The
788 corrected PSFs at the same three field positions, as shown in Fig. S8D) after tilt compensation,
789 demonstrate reduced bias in field dependence compared to those before compensation (Fig. S8B).

790 The advantage of quantifying field dependence in PCA space is robustness. Because the bases
791 of PCA is from all the calibrated PSF data, the vector distance in PCA space reflects global
792 difference, making it less dependent to noise. However, it becomes unconvincing to compare
793 vectors in different PCA spaces. To quantify field dependence in different imaging systems (with
794 and without PSF engineering), we resort to CC.

795 We use PSF dataset in Fig. 2 of main text, as well as the corresponding dataset without PSF
796 engineering (switching off the tetrapod phase mask at the SLM), to demonstrate the influence of
797 PSF engineering on field dependence. As the implementation before, we first detect the tilt of the
798 same imaging system (# 2 of Table S1) without (Fig. S8F) and with (Fig. S8H) PSF engineering.
799 This yields consistent results: the direction cosine along x and y axis of the tilt norm in Fig. S8F is
800 $(0.0020, 0.0030)$, and that in Fig. S8H is $(0.0020, 0.0033)$.

801 With the tilt compensation, we obtain both field dependence quantification results (Fig. S8G
802 and I). The smaller CC value in G reveals that field dependence is exacerbated due to PSF
803 engineering, which might be caused by practical factors, e.g., the placement and operation error of
804 the SLM.

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6. Refractive index mismatch

When refractive index (RI) mismatch exists (Fig. S9A), one needs to consider two axial positions to determine the defocus phase at pupil: the distance of the emitter above the coverslip (γ_e) and the distance of the nominal focal plane (NFP) position above the coverslip (γ_{NFP}). We assume that a positive position is above the coverslip. These two axial parameters have different contributions to the spherical defocus phase at the BFP. The electric field at BFP can be formulated as

$$U_{BFP} = \text{circ}(\rho) \exp(j(M + \gamma_e k_2 \sqrt{1 - (\frac{n_1}{n_2} \rho)^2} - \gamma_{NFP} k_1 \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} + 2\pi(\alpha \frac{x A_M}{\lambda f_{4f}} + \beta \frac{y A_M}{\lambda f_{4f}}))) \quad (\text{S2})$$

812 where

$$\rho = \frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \text{NA}}{r_p n_1} \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$r_p = \frac{f_{4f} \text{NA}}{\sqrt{A_M^2 - \text{NA}^2}} \quad (\text{S4})$$

813 and description of the involved parameters is shown in Table S3. The different contributions
814 can be revealed from the different multiplication factor before γ_e and γ_{NFP} . In the case without RI
815 mismatch, namely, $n_1=n_2$, $k_1=k_2$, these two factors are the same and can be combined according to
816 the associative law, yielding the fact that the spherical defocus phase merely depends on the relative
817 position of the emitter with respect to the NFP.

818 To visualize the RI mismatch influence on PSF, we apply the scalar imaging model (imaging
819 system # 1 of Table S1 where n_1 and n_2 are 1.406 and 1.0 respectively) and compare PSFs at
820 (γ_e, γ_{NFP}) and $(\gamma_e + 0.5, \gamma_{NFP} + 0.5)$. Both PSFs should be the same if there is no such RI
821 mismatch, while this resemblance is broken in mismatch case (Fig. S9C). In order to transform
822 PSFs at $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma_{NFP})$ from the calibration experiments to PSFs at practical $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma_e)$, we rely on the
823 physical imaging model embedded in VIPR [18].

824

7. SMLM simulation and experiment details

7.1. FOV specification

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826 When it comes to a large FOV or high throughput, imaging tasks takes a lot of time. For the FOV-
827 dependent DeepSTORM3D, as a variant of DeepSTORM3D with additional input layers of
828 transverse coordinate maps, it takes several days in training (90000 training images and 10000 test
829 images for both networks) and several seconds in inference to localize emitters of one frame in our
830 case (1371-by-1371 pixels in one frame, 11-by-11 squares of sub-images and 161 pixels in width
831 and height of each sub-image, GPU: NVIDIA TITAN RTX with 24 G memory).

832 To demonstrate our concept in simulation, we think it is reasonable to focus on a FOV smaller
833 than the calibrated large FOV for the sake of time saving. Specifically, our simulation is
834 implemented in the blue area 1 (Fig. S10A) which consists of a 6-by-6 grids of sub-areas with
835 overlapping. Each sub-area has a valid central region (the central shade in Fig. S10A) due to the
836 consideration of PSF truncation at the edge. The ‘‘CCCC’’ micro structure (see the ground truth in
837 Fig. S12) and the sinusoid micro surface (see the reconstructed result in Fig. S13) are set in the
838 transparent blue and yellow region in Fig. S10A respectively. In experiments, we switch to the
839 whole FOV (orange region 2 in Fig. S10A).

7.2. Additional simulation details and results

840 The demonstration of the PPG3D’s contribution in SMLM is built upon a valid comparison between
841 FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D and regular DeepSTORM3D. Importantly, the localization
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844 numbers from both networks should be the same. As we mentioned in the main text, both networks
845 yield different numbers of inference under the same post-processing threshold [11]. To address this
846 difference, we resort to an inference confidence filter and density filter of ThunderSTORM (an
847 ImageJ plugin) and finally obtain around 0.85 million valid predictions from both networks for the
848 comparison of “CCCC” structure. This number is 0.35 million for sinusoid surface (Fig. S13).

849 **7.3. Additional experiment details and results**

850 In SMLM experiment, the number of valid localizations for the mitochondria (Fig. 5) is around
851 12.7 million and that number is 11.5 million for the microtubule reconstruction (Fig. S14A) and 3.2
852 million for an additional microtubule imaging in (Fig. S14B).

854

855 **Fig. S1.**

856 **Optical imaging system and phase masks.** (A) Imaging system composed of an inverted Nikon
 857 microscope and a 4f optical extension with a phase modulator (spatial light modulator, SLM for
 858 short, or diffractive optical element, DOE for short) at the back focal plane (BFP) for PSF
 859 engineering. IIP denotes intermediate image plane. Bead samples, a nanohole array and cells with
 860 fluorescently labeled mitochondria or microtubules were used. Either on SLM or with DOE, we
 861 employed phase masks for Tetrapod (B), double helix (C), astigmatism (D), as well as a learned
 862 PSF (E). Note that we also use a cylindrical lens in front of a camera for astigmatism PSF
 863 engineering.

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866 **Fig. S2.**

867 **PPG3D implementation details.** (A) Three selected field/lateral positions (green) around the target
 868 position (orange). (B) Six searched/spatial positions (blue) around the target position (orange). (C)
 869 An example of a 2D lateral interpolation regarding principal component coefficients. (D) An
 870 example of a 1D axial interpolation.
 871

873

874 **Fig. S3.**

875 **Comparison details of spatially variant PSF characterization methods.** (A) The retrieved pupil
 876 phase from VIPR at field position P_0 in Fig. 2A. (B) Retrieved phase from ZPPR21 with at field
 877 position P_0 (21 Zernike basis functions, the maximum degree of the code we can access [19]). (C)
 878 An example of 2D interpolation of Zernike coefficients in shift-variant ZPPR21 implementation.
 879 The blue dots and red cross dots are the “seen” calibration positions and “unseen” test positions
 880 respectively. PSF generation by CSpline (code: https://github.com/dafeixiao/CSpline_test, adapted
 881 from <https://github.com/ZhuangLab/storm-analysis>) at seen (D) and unseen (E) axial positions. In
 882 both D and E, the first and second row are PSFs, normalized in [0, 1], from CSpline and
 883 measurement respectively. The third row shows the absolute difference between the first and the
 884 second row with a magnification factor of 8. (F-G) Comparison of field dependence
 885 characterization performance between PPG3D and shift-variant ZPPR21 using astigmatism PSF,
 886 as a complement of 21-degree comparison in Tetrapod PSF. F is CC assessment of ZPPR21 and
 887 PPG3D at five test positions. G shows generated PSFs at the $z = -0.9$ μm of the five lateral test
 888 positions. (H) shows a comprehensive comparison of astigmatism PSF characterization by ZPPR21
 889 and PPG3D, in terms of accuracy (CC) and speed.

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Fig. S4.

Double helix PSF dataset analysis using PPG3D. (A) CC assessment at seen and unseen (on grids) axial positions. (B) 5 out of total 5 principal components (PCs) with their explained variance percentages on the top. (C) Interpolated PSFs at several unseen positions and the measured ground truth (GT) PSFs, for different z values. (D) CC assessment of global interpolation (blue and orange represent see and unseen field positions respectively) with calibrated lateral locations (bottom projection) and CC projection to the left yz plane, accompanied by a CC heatmap (polynomial fit with an order of 4) on the right. (E) Generated and measured PSFs at $z=0 \mu\text{m}$ of the five test field positions. P1-P5 correspond to, at the bottom projection in D, left, right, middle, bottom, and top orange circles, respectively.

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Fig. S5.

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Astigmatism PSF dataset analysis using PPG3D. (A) CC assessment at seen and unseen (on grid) axial positions. (B) 5 out of total 5 principal components (PCs) with their explained variance percentages on the top. (C) Interpolated PSFs at several unseen positions and the measured ground truth (GT) PSFs. (D) CC assessment of global interpolation (blue and orange represent seen and unseen field positions respectively) with calibrated locations (bottom projection) and CC projection to the left yz plane, accompanied by a CC heatmap (polynomial fit with an order of 4) on the right. (E) Generated and measured PSFs at z=0 μm of the five test field positions. P1-P5 correspond to, at the bottom projection in D, left, right, middle, bottom, and top orange circles, respectively.

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Fig. S6.

Learned PSF dataset analysis using PPG3D. (A) CC assessment at seen and unseen (on grid) axial positions. (B) 5 out of total 11 principal components (PCs) with their explained variance percentages on the top. (C) Interpolated PSFs at several unseen positions and the measured ground truth (GT) PSFs. (D) CC assessment of global interpolation (blue and orange represent see and unseen field positions respectively) with calibrated locations (bottom projection) and CC projection to the left yz plane, accompanied by a CC heatmap (polynomial fit with an order of 4) on the right. (E) Generated and measured PSFs at z=0 μm of the five test field positions. P1-P5 correspond to, at the bottom projection in D, left, right, middle, bottom, and top orange circles, respectively.

930

931 **Fig. S7.**

932 **Analysis of calibration density and noise.** (A) PSF generation accuracy at different density levels.
 933 Blue stars represent average CC over all seen and unseen spatial positions and the orange line is a
 934 polynomial fitting result. The densities at square B and C are visualized in (B) and (C). (D)
 935 Generated PSFs at $z=0 \mu\text{m}$ of the 5 unseen test positions and the measured ground truth. (E) CC
 936 between the interpolated PSF stack and the ground truth at different levels of shot noise. At level
 937 G, the interpolated PSFs at several unseen axial positions and the ground truth are shown in (G).
 938 (F) CC at different levels of read-out noise. At level H, the interpolated PSF at several test positions
 939 and the ground truth are shown in (H).

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943 **Fig. S8.**

944 **Field dependence characterization with tilt detection.** (A) an image of a nano-hole array. (B)
945 Characterization through PCA-based distance without tilt compensation. Three PSFs at the red spots
946 are shown below. (C) Contour of the detected tilt plane with a direction cosine of -0.0063
947 along x and -0.0003 along y . (D) Field dependence characterization with tilt compensation where
948 three PSFs at the red spots (same as B) are shown below. (E-I) Influence of PSF engineering on
949 field dependence quantification. E, FOV of the imaging system (the same as Fig. 2A) with
950 calibrated field positions. The zoom-in view shows the PSF in two cases: without and with PSF
951 engineering. The former yields tilt detection F and the field dependence quantification G through
952 CC metric and the latter yields H and I.

954

955 **Fig. S9.**

956 **Refractive index mismatch.** (A-B) Illustration of RI mismatch in microscopy. (C) Influence of RI
 957 mismatch on PSFs at a series of axial pairs (γ_e, γ_{NFP}).
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Fig. S10.

Illustration of the calibration positions and FOV explanation in STORM experiments. (A) Calibration of Tetrapod PSF. The background is one experimental image with green dots specifying calibration positions throughout the FOV. For the “CCCC” (Fig. 4) and sinusoidal surface (Fig. S13) simulation, region 1 covered with 6-by-6 overlapping blue squares (sub image regions of 161 pixels) was used. The two shade squares at center presents one sub region and its valid central area (PSFs close to the edge are possibly truncated, thus are invalid). The blue shade rectangle with transparency is the exact area for “CCCC” simulation and the yellow one is for the sinusoidal surface simulation. The orange rectangle region 2 shows the FOV in SMLM experiment with a width of 178 μm . (B) Calibration of the STORM experiment with astigmatism PSF. The bottom PSF row shows astigmatism stack at the FOV center.

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Fig. S11.

Accuracy and precision analysis in a quarter of a calibrated FOV (Fig. S10A). (A) RMSE accuracy distribution, from FOV-Dependent DeepSTORM3D, based on a simulated image with 240 emitters randomly located in the $z=2 \mu\text{m}$ plane. The black dots show the localization RMSE whose polynomial surface fitting (the grid surface) yields a contour at the bottom. In precision analysis (C-F for FOV-Dependent DeepSTORM3D and G-I for DeepSTORM3D), 36 emitters uniformly distributed in the $z=2 \mu\text{m}$ plane (B) were localized 100 times. (C) total 3600 localizations (blue dots), with the true lateral positions at the bottom (orange dots). (D-F) x, y and z localization precision (STD: standard deviation) with their polynomial surface fitting. (G-I) The same analysis on DeepSTORM3D for precision comparison.

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985 **Fig. S12.**

986 **Simulated dotted tubule "CCCC" structure.** (A) The cross section of the tubule unit (B). Each
 987 "C" includes four tubule units and the combination of the four letters is shown in (C). The axial
 988 locations of the four letters are $0.6\ \mu\text{m}$, $1.6\ \mu\text{m}$, $2.6\ \mu\text{m}$, and $3.6\ \mu\text{m}$ respectively. The whole 3D
 989 micro structure (D) has 9 "CCCC" units.

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992 **Fig. S13.**

993 **Simulation of a sinusoidal surface in SMLM.** (A) Ground truth of the surface's cross section.
 994 The reconstructed surface, by FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D, is projected at the y-z plane (B)
 995 and x-y plane (C). The red arrow shows z axis. Scale bar: 4 μm . Cross sections (D₁) and (D₂) of the
 996 white line in B presents localization results by FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (subscript 1) and
 997 DeepSTORM3D (subscript 2) respectively. The zoom-in views of squares E, F, and G are shown
 998 in (E₁), (E₂), (F₁), (F₂), (G₁), and (G₂), which demonstrates improvements due to field dependence
 999 consideration.

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Fig. S14.

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Large-FOV super-resolution imaging of microtubules with Tetrapod PSF. (A) Maximum projection of the reconstructed 3D microtubule in a 130-by-131 μm FOV through FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D. Scale bar: 20 μm . The structure in square B at the depth of ~ 100 nm is shown in (B₁) and (B₂) with subscript 1 representing FOV-dependent-DeepSTORM3D and 2 for DeepSTORM3D. The structure in square C at the depth of 3900 nm is similarly shown in (C₁) and (C₂). Scale bar: 2 μm . (D) An additional super-resolution imaging of microtubules. Scale bar: 20 μm . The reconstructed structure in the square E at the depth of 97.5 nm is shown in (E₁) and (E₂). The structure in square F at the depth of 3900 nm is similarly shown in (F₁) and (F₂). Scale bar: 1 μm .

1013

Optical imaging system	Microscope	4-f setup		
		Focal length of both lenses	Phase modulator	Camera
# 1	Nikon ECLEPSE Ti2 inverted microscope	100 mm	SLM, Meadowlark, pixel size: 9.2 μm , resolution: 1152x1920	Teledyne Photometrics Prime 95B, pixel size: 11 μm , resolution: 1200x1200
# 2	Nikon ECLEPSE Ti2 inverted microscope	200 mm	A Tetrapod DOE, fabricated by lithography	Teledyne Photometrics Kinetix, pixel size: 6.5 μm (2 x binning is used), resolution: 3200x3200

1014

Table S1.

1015

Compositions and parameters of imaging systems.

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Sample	Details
Beads (fluorescent microspheres)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • excitation/emission wavelength: 625/645 nm, diameter: 200 nm. • mixed with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution, coated on a coverslip on a spin coater. • The medium of the sample is air (refractive index of 1.0) or water (refractive index of 1.33) by dropping distilled water above.
Nano-hole array	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • consist of 50-by-50 holes with a diameter of 200 nm and an interval of 20 μm from each other. • fabricated on a coverslip with a chrome coating of 100 nm thickness, drilled by ion beam etching (IBE).
Cells	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • label mitochondria or microtubules. • Labeling details in Methods of the main text.

1017 **Table S2.**
1018 Details of samples.
1019

Parameter	Description
(x, y)	Cartesian coordinates at BFP
ρ	Normalized polar coordinate at BFP
$(\alpha, \beta, \gamma_e)$	Cartesian coordinates of an emitter, γ_e is the relative distance above the coverslip
γ_{NFP}	The distance of the nominal focal plane above the coverslip
M	Phase mask at BFP
A_M	Magnification of the objective
n_1, k_1, n_2, k_2	Refractive index of the medium between coverslip and objective, corresponding wave number, refractive index of the medium inside the sample, corresponding wave number
λ	Wave length of the emission light
f_{4f}	Focal length of the first lens in the 4-f setup
$circ(\rho)$	A circular window with 1 inside and 0 outside. The window radius is NA/n_1 for oil objective and supercritical angle fluorescence can be included

1020 **Table S3.**
1021 Parameter table.
1022

PSF	Number of field positions (x-y)	Axial positions (z)/ μm	Cropping width and height in pixels	Diameter of calibration region/ μm
Double helix	437	-1:0.1:1	25	170.95
Astigmatism	383	-1:0.1:1	31	164.26
Learned PSF	340	-1.5:0.1:1.5	31	170.17

1023 **Table S4.**
1024 Calibration datasets. The calibration region is approximately circular and the average of the x and
1025 y range of all the calibrated positions is defined as the diameter.
1026

Axial interpolation (Input: 15 PSFs. Test: 14 PSFs)			
Methods	Language	Device	Time specifications
ZPPR21	Matlab	GPU and CPU	Phase retrieval: 8.02 s PSF generation at all 29 axial positions: 0.93 s
VIPR	Matlab	GPU	Phase retrieval: 19.92s PSF generation at all 29 axial positions: 0.13 s
Cspline	Python	CPU	Build the Spliner for Cspline interpolation: 283.46 s PSF generation at all 29 axial positions: 13.49 s
PPG3D	Python	CPU	PCA and PSF generation at all 29 axial positions: 0.05 s
Global interpolation (Input: 146×29 PSFs. Test: 5×29 PSFs)			
Methods	Language	Device	Time specifications
ZPPR21	Matlab	GPU and CPU	Phase retrieval for all seen field positions: 1170.92 s Coefficient fitting: 1.23 s PSF generation at all 5×29 axial positions: 4.65 s
PPG3D	Python	CPU	PPG3D formation: 0.85 s PSF generation at all 5×29 axial positions: 1.70 s

1027 **Table S5.**
1028 Runtime specifications of Fig. 2.
1029
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1032 **Movie S1.**

1033 Blinking video example in the mitochondria STORM experiment with Tetrapod PSF. Scale bar:
1034 20 μm .

1035 **Movie S2.**

1036 Axial scanning video of the reconstructed 3D super-resolved mitochondria through Tetrapod PSF
1037 and FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D. Scale bar: 20 μm .

1038 **Movie S3.**

1039 Rotation demonstration of the reconstructed 3D super-resolved mitochondria through Tetrapod
1040 PSF and FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (Fig. 5). Hereafter, the z range is rendered with a
1041 scaling factor of 2 to ease axial visualization. Scale bar: 20 μm .

1042 **Movie S4.**

1043 Rotation demonstration of a region of interest in the reconstructed 3D super-resolved
1044 mitochondria in Fig. 5. Scale bar: 10 μm .

1045 **Movie S5.**

1046 Rotation demonstration of the reconstructed 3D super-resolved microtubules through astigmatism
1047 PSF and FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (Fig. 6). Scale bar: 20 μm .

1048 **Movie S6.**

1049 Rotation demonstration of the reconstructed 3D super-resolved mitochondria through astigmatism
1050 PSF and FOV-dependent DeepSTORM3D (Fig. 6). Scale bar: 20 μm .

1051 **Movie S7.**

1052 Rotation demonstration of the reconstructed simulated “CCCC” structure from FOV-dependent
1053 DeepSTORM3D in Fig. 4. Scale bar: 20 μm .

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